

GLOBAL INTERNET ETHICS AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN PROVIDING FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article given the information about the emergence of the concept of Internet ethics, its peculiarities and its importance today in the spiritual and moral development of young people.

Keywords: information, information attack, information consumption, fake information, informative, ethics, information culture, internet, internet etiquette, computer ethics, social network.

The 21st century is as a period of rapid life, comprehensive information system and telecommunication technology development in the world, should include things that should support life and human activities, as well as the globalization of the information space has been treated as a past factor if it affects the development of the whole world. In modern conditions, special attention is paid to the protection of the younger generation from the effects of harmful information, the development of ideological immunity in the fight against information attacks. In particular, in the United States, France, Germany and Russia have developed the program named “Safe Internet”.

According to Professor Y.N.Zasurskiy: “Global networks play an important role in the international information space. In addition, the Internet guarantees freedom of speech in the field of information”[1]. However, under the concept of “freedom of speech”, most users mean to use the global network as they wish, without following any rules, ethical norms. From the above considerations, it can be seen that inculcating the rules of internet ethics in young people has become a topical issue today.

The emergence of the concept of “The ethics of Internet“ is interpreted differently in different sources. According to Russian media researcher A.Skvortsov, the idea of introducing ethical rules in the global network is associated with the emergence in 1989 of an anonymous group of Internet activists. The manifesto was accepted by them, according to which the filth on the Internet:

- illegal entrance to Internet resources;
- violation of the completeness of publicly available information;
- disclosure of other users' secrets [2].

However, there are specific aspects of working on the Internet, first of all, a journalist must follow the following rules when running his website, social network page and editorial blog or website:

- not to post information without checking its source several times;
- not to use quotes, photos or videos from social networks without indicating the source;
- understand that photos taken on social networks and published will not have any other content when posted on the organization's page or blog;
- not to post photos, videos on the Internet without the consent of the people depicted in them;
- they must express their personal views and political views on the page of the organization. It should always be kept in mind that an organization's website on the Internet should only serve to shape a positive image of the organization. Also, on the organization's website and social network page, another organization should not post materials that unjustifiably criticize the employee;
- to respect author's authorship rights and must escape from plagiarism.

Population growth in Uzbekistan is increasing the demand for the Internet. In particular, in 2020 the population of Uzbekistan will exceed more 34 million [3], and the number of Internet users will exceed 22 million[4].

In developed countries, at least 500,000 sites serve the same population. When it comes to the our country, we have 77,000 [5] sites, which in turn is not enough to provide information to the population.

In addition, on February 19, 2018, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the ICT sector" was issued. The decree listed the factors hindering the rapid development of the Internet and information security. In particular, it was noted that the telecommunications infrastructure is underdeveloped, remote areas of the country are not provided with telecommunications networks, the quality of mobile communications and the Internet does not meet the needs of the population[6].

As a result of the analysis of the above considerations, it can be said that the following reasons make it necessary for the formation of Internet ethics skills in today's youth:

- commenting on the content of public policy, which affects the minds of our youth, aimed at protecting the interests of future generations, the lack of rapid development of Internet journalism, which provides rapid coverage of issues of interest to future generations, as well as a wide range of critical and analytical coverage of youth issues;
- the formation of various destructive ideas among young people;
- Introduction of "Mass Culture" through foreign sites;
- Increased crime and fraud on the Internet;

- an increase in sites promoting violence and savagery;
- increase in the number of sites promoting drug addiction and pornography;
- The development of online games and its growing negative impact on young people;
- It is observed that religious extremist organizations carry out propaganda work among young people through foreign sites.

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